

Chronicle of a Post-October 7 "Middle East Order" Foretold

Pinar Bilgin

Pinar Bilgin is a Professor of International Relations at Bilkent University. She is the author of Regional Security in the Middle East: A Critical Perspective (Routledge, 2nd ed. 2019), The International in Security, Security in the International (Routledge 2016), Thinking Globally About World Politics (with Karen Smith) (Palgrave 2024).

Introduction

My title invokes Gabriel Garcia Marquez's novel *Chronicle of a Death Foretold*, which narrates an honor killing in reverse chronology. The story begins with a killing, and readers learn that almost everyone knew about it but did not prevent it. Three critical themes run through the author's narrative that resonate with our analysis: societal conformism, abdication of collective responsibility, and complicity. These dynamics provide a poignant lens for examining the regional response to the 7 October 2023 attacks and its aftermath. For, there is nothing fundamentally "new" about what we have witnessed since 7 October. While the scale of destruction is unprecedented in our lifetime, the methods used by Israel are not. For years, Israel has been testing and resetting the limits of the laws of war in its conduct of urban warfare (Gordon 2023). The regional actors' abdication of collective responsibility, conformism, and complicity is also not new. I contend that what we have observed since 7 October is emblematic of an order that began to form after the Iraqi invasion of Kuwait in 1991, surfaced after the Oslo Accords in 1993, and crystallized in the 2020 Abraham Accords. I will briefly examine these three mileposts in the making of the not-so-new Middle East

order.

The Gulf War: Abdicating Collective Responsibility

The 1991 Iraqi invasion of Kuwait was a turning point that allowed some regional actors to abdicate what had long been viewed as an Arab collective responsibility towards Palestinians. Since then, individual Arab states have found it easier to break from the rest of the Arab World and establish closer security relations with the United States and (covertly) Israel.

By establishing the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) in 1981, the Gulf states had signaled their differing insecurities from the rest of the Arab world. Still, they had found it difficult not to toe the line on the Israel/Palestine issue, fearing Arab public opinion. In 1991, by failing to condemn the Iraqi invasion of Kuwait, PLO leader Yasser Arafat inadvertently provided GCC members with an opportunity to distance themselves from the Palestinian cause.

Notwithstanding their differences, GCC members share a significant characteristic: they are rentier states with weak relationships with their citizens. While civil society is cons-

trained, activists have historically found ways to express solidarity with the Palestinian cause, as this has been one of the few issues that permit limited dissent from the regime. Following the 1991 war, GCC members used Arafat's position as a pretext to decrease their reliance on Palestinian and other Arab labor. This move had consequences for civil societal activism about the Palestinian cause in that workers who had historically played critical roles in organizing local oil embargoes or staging anti-regime protests when they thought insufficient action was taken to address Palestinian suffering were replaced with more precarious Southeast Asian laborers.

The Oslo Accords: Getting Comfortable in Conformism

The 1993 Oslo Accords expanded the opening allowed by the 1991 war, with Arab states adapting to new rules. In 1994, Jordan signed a peace treaty with Israel, while others began exploring relations with Israel despite the limitations of the Oslo Accords.

At the time, Edward Said highlighted the cynicism of both Yitzhak Rabin and Yasser Arafat in signing the Oslo Accords. Said considered Arafat's position cynical because he signed the agreement without fully understanding the situation in Israel and the occupied territories, having been in exile for decades. With the Oslo Accords, Israel gained recognition without returning significant land, acknowledging Palestinian sovereignty, or addressing the refugee issue. Meanwhile, Arafat returned to the West Bank and assumed leadership of the newly formed Palestinian Authority. Essentially, Oslo was a lifeline for Arafat, who had lost his grip on the Palestinian people, as seen during the first Intifada and after his isolation in 1991.

For Rabin, it was cynical because he brought Arafat back to police Palestinians. As he stated, "I prefer the Palestinians to cope with the problem of enforcing order in the Gaza [Strip]... They will rule there by their methods, freeing... the Israeli army soldiers from having to do what they will do" (quoted in Said 1995, 7). This statement reveals the accords' underlying rationale, prioritizing Israeli control from the outset of the peace process.

Hamas's 2006 victory in the Palestinian Legislative Council elections occurred amid increasing authoritarian rule by the Palestinian Authority. It is ironic, if not tragic, that Israeli authorities now use the 2006 elections to justify targeting Palestinians in Gaza as Hamas supporters, despite the historical support Israel provided to Hamas to sow discord among Palestinians. By the mid-2000s, the desire for normalcy was so high among Palestinians and the broader Arab public that even after Israel's lack of commitment to its obligations became evident, there was no overwhelming pressure on Arab states to sever ties with Israel. Many regional states (including Türkiye) strengthened their ties with Israel during this period, politically, economically, or through intelligence, even as some maintained the façade of non-recognition at the diplomatic level.

The Abraham Accords: Complicity Institutionalised

When the Abraham Accords were signed in 2020, the United States touted them as an effort to normalize relations between Israel and those Arab states that wanted to show a united front against Iran. The group soon began to expand, with Morocco joining Bahrain and UAE. At the time of the 7 October attacks, Saudi Arabia was rumored to be close to

joining. What is left unsaid in this narrative is that the Abraham Accords also provided the Arab signatories with access to Israel's unparalleled surveillance technology and spyware capabilities. Indeed, the agreement has served a dual function: legitimizing Israel's military control over the occupied Palestinian territories while simultaneously entrenching the Arab signatories' regime-security-focused (previously covert) military and intelligence ties with Israel (Grinberg 2023).

After the October 7 attack by Hamas and the subsequent Israeli devastation of Gaza, even as Israel's breach of the laws of war became impossible to overlook, regional actors found themselves in a bind. If they aligned with public opinion and threw their weight behind the Palestinian cause, they risked alienating Israel. Such a move would also potentially jeopardize their access to Israeli surveillance technology, spyware, and intelligence capabilities, which are critical components in maintaining their authoritarian rule against domestic dissent. While the horrific nature of Hamas's 7 October attack provided the context for inaction in the short term, as Israel's military campaign progressed throughout 2024 and even extended into Lebanon, the degree of institutionalization of regional actors' complicity became increasingly evident.

Conclusion

As in Marquez's novel, the "Middle East order" unfolding before us was, in many ways, foretold. The 1991 Gulf War marked a turning point away from collective Arab responsibility toward the Palestinians, and the Oslo Accords underscored the region's move towards conformism, setting a precedent for the Abraham Accords, which institutionalized complicity in Israel's actions.

The regional actors' inability to respond to the humanitarian catastrophe in Gaza reflects not a sudden shift but the endpoint of years of prioritizing regime security over solidarity with Palestinians. ♦

References

Said, Edward W. 1995. *Peace and its Discontents: Essays on Palestine in the Middle East Peace Process*. New York: Vintage.

Gordon, Neve (interview by Linda Tabar). 2023. "Israel and the Laws of War: A Conversation with Neve Gordon." *Middle East Report* (November 14). <https://merip.org/2023/11/israel-and-the-laws-of-war-a-conversation-with-neve-gordon/>

Grinberg, Yoav. 2023. "The Abraham Accords and Cybersecurity." *Middle East Report* (September 14). <https://merip.org/2023/09/the-abraham-accords-cybersecurity/>